

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SPEECH ETIQUETTE OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH YOUTH

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Abstract.

This article investigates around the appearance of speech etiquette of English and Uzbek youth, similarities and differences between them. The impact of cultural and social factors on speech etiquette is also discussed.

Keywords: Speech etiquette, manners, retort, forms of address, forms of speech.

Language has a great place not only in human life, but also in society, and it is considered the main means of interpersonal communication. We all know that language is a factor that helps a person to express himself, to understand, and to establish relations with the surrounding society and culture. Language not only serves the processes of communication and information exchange, but also shows the stages of development of society and culture, social life. After all, as stated in many scientific sources, language is a mirror of society. [1]

In today's developed society, being able to use the language skillfully, conducting speech activities in compliance with the rules of etiquette in interpersonal relations is a manifestation of moral culture. As time goes by, people are paying more attention to etiquette, and trying to follow it as much as possible. [2]

If we take a closer look at the history of etiquette and its rules, the word etiquette is derived from the French word *estiquette*, which means to stick, to fasten. [3.585] The French king Louis XIV caused this word to enter the conversation. Louis XIV ordered court officials to hang signs known as *estiquettes* as a reminder not to cut certain areas of the royal palace garden. In this way, a set of rules of etiquette was formed in the community, which was limited or could not be considered to do certain things, and were united under the rules of etiquette. Today, following etiquette rules and standards has become one of the forms of education. When a baby is born, after a while, as soon as it begins to speak and move, its parents begin to teach it the first rules of etiquette, that is, it is told to greet others and shake hands as a way of saying goodbye. It can be seen from this that the norms of etiquette are instilled in the mind of the child from the moment he knows it.

The unique importance of speech etiquette units is that they emerge on the basis of social factors. According to the age of the interlocutors, we can divide the speech of the elderly and young people. The speech of the elderly is characterized by the use of old-age proverbs and sayings, softness in speech, and the use of a warning tone. In the speech of young people, the use of new words and expressions, the mixing of words from different languages, and the use of abbreviations are seen. In this article, the signs of speech etiquette of English and Uzbek youth will be covered in detail.

Comparing the speech of Uzbek and English youth, we can find some peculiarities, similarities and differences between them. The English people are known to the whole world with their gentleness, nobility, and kindness. In the speech act of young English people, the

polite and soft tone characteristic of the English people is visible. When starting communication on the street, in public places, young people mainly begin the conversation with the words hello, hi or Are you alright? How are you? . The main purpose of using the above-mentioned interrogative sentence is not to ask the interlocutor about his health, but simply as an introductory sentence to start the conversation. Young English people prefer small talk that starts with the weather, the environment, and this is considered as normal, [4] Uzbek youth do not use a short greeting like English people in the communication process. In the speech process of young people, there are elements of conversation, such as long greetings, inquiries about daily news. As an example, let's take the examples below:

- Assalomu alaykum, do'stlar, men keldim, bormisizlar, omonmisizlar?
- Keling, keling, Safuraxon, qalaysiz, salomatmisiz? Zerikmayapsizmi? Nima yangiliklar? /Erkin A'zimov, Bayramdan boshqa kunlar/.

It can be seen that young Uzbeks, along with the greeting at the beginning of the conversation, use conversation replicas about the health of the partner, news in his personal life.

When English youth addresses unfamiliar people Hey, you there!, Hey, there!, Young man!, Young lady! they use compounds that are said to attract attention, [5] as an alternative form of these compounds, Uzbek youth Hoy! Hey! Hey guy! Hey girl! uses units. If English people communicate with acquaintances or close people, they start the conversation with words such as friend, bestie, chum, pal, buddy, words like man, do'st, oshna, o'rtoq are applied among Uzbek people.

In recent years, it has become a tradition among young people around the world to mix words from other languages into their mother tongue. English and Uzbek youth are no exception. This situation is especially evident in the speech of Uzbek youth. The policy of russification, which lasted for many years, absorbed the Russian language not only in the speech of the elderly, but also in the youth. As a result, it has become fashionable to mix Uzbek and Russian among young people:

- Bargish, buningni qarab yurmasang, yo'qolib qoladi, smotri!
- Sestra, biz sizdan hafa bo'ldik, ketamiz endi.
- Xvatit, ketsangiz keting tezroq! /Erkin A'zimov, Bayramdan boshqa kunlar/
- O'zi ko'nglingiz bormi unda?
- Konechno! Juda bor-da!
- Gaplashaylikmi u bilan?
- Vi cho'! Esrlaringni yebsizlar!
- Yigitni ko'rdingizmi o'zi?
- Ko'rdim.
- Qanaqa ekan?
- Obbo! Bo'ldi endi iltimos! Bir kami uni ta'riflashim qoluvdi. Kinder-surpriz. Ponyatno. /Nazokat Azim. Idora etilganlar/

Among English youth, Spanish is becoming more popular and even surpasses French in this regard. The main reason for this is that Spanish is very easy to learn due to its relatively simple grammar, which in turn has increased the demand for learning this language among young English people. As a result of the mixing of the two languages, the phenomenon of Spanglish arose: [6]

1. Lets get lonche before we finish shopping. (lonche- lunch)
2. My friend is having a pari! (pari-party)
3. Watcha! There is a dog in the road! (watcha-watch out)
4. Can you pick up some eggs at la marketa? (marketa-market).

From the above, we can conclude that young people adjusting in both languages have their own rules and norms of speech etiquette. The origin and survival of these norms directly depend on their lifestyle, socio-cultural situation, outlook and thoughts. Nevertheless, we can see that there are appropriate and different aspects between the speech etiquette of Uzbek and English youth.

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